

NOTES

A Note on Bardhan-Sengupta Synthesis

Amareshwar Chatterjee and Dilip Banerjee

In view of our interest¹ in the study of alkylations of cyclic β -ketoesters with different alkyl halides under different solvent conditions, it was of importance to reinvestigate some aspect of Bardhan-Sengupta² synthesis. This phenanthrene synthesis found its most fruitful application in other fields also.

The first step of this reaction is the condensation of potassium enolate of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I) in benzene with β -phenethyl bromide(II). The condensation product³(III) was isolated in 48% yield. It was reported by the authors that the

sodio enolate of (I) is not suitable for this type of alkylation and many unsuccessful attempts were made to interact it with (II).

We have now found that the alkylation of (I) with (II) occurs readily even in the presence of sodium metal if dimethylformamide (DMF) is used in combination with benzene as the reaction medium. It has been observed that the sodio enolate of (I) is insoluble but the potassium enolate is soluble in benzene. When DMF was added to the suspension of sodio salt of (I) under benzene, the salt completely went into solution and a reasonably good yield of the alkylated product (III) was realised. The nature of the ion pair³ is therefore the main reason for the success (when K is used) and failure (in case of Na) of the authors in this alkylation reaction.

When the sodio enolate from (I) was alkylated in a mixture of DMF and xylene to attain a higher temperature the alkylated material (III) was obtained only in 32% yield even after 28 hours of refluxing, the major product being a residue which could not be distilled. To get a better yield of the alkylated product, potassium derivative of (I) was refluxed (9 or 28 hours) with (II) in a mixture of benzene and DMF; but again the yield

1. A. Chatterjee, D. Banerjee and S. Banerjee, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 3851.
2. J. C. Bardhan and S. C. Sengupta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2520, 2798.
3. H. O. House, "Modern Synthetic Reactions", W. A. Benjamin Inc., New York, 1965, p. 176 and the references cited therein.

of the desired product (III) was only 36%, significantly lower than that reported by Bardhan *et al.*² It may be mentioned here that Kon⁴ obtained a 65% yield of the condensation product (III) by interacting potassium enolate of (I) with (II) in boiling xylene solution.

From this study, it appears that the alkyl halide of the type (II) is probably destroyed by a side reaction such as dehydrohalogenation⁵ especially when DMF is used as a co-solvent at a moderately high temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 1-β-Phenethylcyclohexan-2-one-1-carboxylate (III).—To a stirred suspension of sodium dust (1.5 g) under dry benzene (50 ml) was added dropwise with cooling a solution of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I, 10 g) in dry benzene (20 ml). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Next day the separated sodium salt was treated with β-phenethyl bromide (12 g.) and DMF (28 ml) when sodium salt completely passed into solution. After 3.4 hr. of stirring at room temperature, sodium bromide began to separate and the stirring was continued for 4 hours more. After 16 hours at room temperature, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 28 hours on the steam bath. It was then diluted with large volume of water, benzene layer separated and the aqueous layer was extracted 2 times with ether. The combined solvent was washed repeatedly with water, dried and evaporated. The residue was distilled under vacuum to furnish the unchanged β-ketoester (I, 3.1 g), b.p. 90-92°/5 mm and the desired product (III) (8.19 g, 51%), b.p. 158-160°/0.4 mm. Redistillation afforded material, b.p. 150-152°/0.2-0.3 mm., i.r. (CHCl₃): 1725, 1715 and 1605 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 74.41; H, 8.21. Calc. for C₁₇H₂₂O₃: C, 74.42; H, 8.08%). This ester is a colourless viscous oil of pleasant odour and gives no colouration with FeCl₃ as reported by Bardhan *et al.*²

When the refluxing time was reduced to 9 hours, the alkylated product (III) was obtained in 45.6% yield, the rest being the unchanged β-ketoester.

Alkylation using sodium metal in xylene and DMF.—The insoluble sodium enolate prepared from (I, 10 g) and sodium dust (1.5 g.) under xylene (70 ml) was treated with the alkyl bromide (II, 12.5 g) and DMF (28 ml). The homogeneous solution on stirring deposited some salt as a paste. After 16 hours at room temperature, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 28 hours. Working up as above afforded unchanged material (I, 500 mg) and the desired product (III) (5.15 g, 32%). The residue (5 g, approx.) could not be distilled even at 220°/0.3 mm, decomposition started during attempted distillation.

Alkylation using potassium metal in benzene and DMF.—The soluble potassium enolate prepared from the ester (I, 8 g) under dry benzene (65 ml) was treated with the bromide (II, 9.6 g) and DMF (26 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred and after 16 hours at room temperature, refluxed for 9 hours. Working up as before afforded the unchanged

4. G. A. R. Kon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1081.

5. Cf. D. Rosenthal and K. H. Davis, (Jr), *J. Chem. Soc.*, (C), 1966, 1973.

β -ketoester (I, 4.19 g) and the desired product (III) (4.6 g, 36%). Longer refluxing period (28 hours) gave the same result.

The authors are thankful to East India Pharmaceutical Works Limited for awarding a scholarship (to D. B.), to U.G.C. for financial assistance and to Prof. B. K. Bhattacharyya for encouragement.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA-32.

Received, August, 26, 1967.